

4-Thiazolidinones XVIII. 3-Aryl-2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidinones Derived from sym-Diarylthioureas.

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sym-Diarylthioureas condense with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to give 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones. By passing dry hydrogen chloride gas in dry benzene solution of the 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones, the corresponding hydrochlorides have been prepared. Nematicidal, insecticidal, acaricidal and fungicidal activities of some of 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been reported. Some of the compounds showed considerable fungicidal activity.

LOCAL anaesthetic,^{1,2} anticonvulsant,^{3,4} fungicidal,⁵⁻⁸ antitubercular,⁹ amoebacidal,¹⁰ antibacterial,¹¹ antiepileptic,¹² antithyroid,¹³ and other biological properties⁵ have been reported earlier for 4-thiazolidinones. As part of a systematic search for potentially biologically active compounds,^{5,14} several new 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones containing halo, hydroxy, nitro and pyridyl groups have been synthesised, by the condensation of various *sym*-diarylthioureas with monochloroacetic acid in ethanolic medium in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The halogen substituted thioureas condense easily with monochloroacetic acid, whereas the hydroxyaryl, nitroaryl and pyridyl substituted thioureas react less readily.

The *sym*-diarylthioureas required in the above condensation were prepared by the method of Rathke¹⁵ and Rao.¹⁶

The nematicidal, insecticidal, acaricidal and fungicidal activity of some 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazoli-

dinones were determined and the results are summarised in the end.

Experimental

Sym-Di-o-fluorophenylthiourea : *o*-Fluoroaniline (30 g.), carbon disulphide (30 ml.), ethanol (40 ml.) and 40% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (25 ml.) were refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hr. At the completion of the reaction the excess of carbon disulphide and ethanol were distilled off. The solid residue was washed several times with hot water by decantation. The product was collected and washed well with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove unreacted amine and any potassium hydroxide and finally with water. The crude thiourea thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol to give yellow shining crystals.

The physical properties and analytical data of the new *sym*-diarylthioureas prepared as above are enlisted in Table I.

TABLE I—*sym*-DI-ARYLTHIOUREAS

S.No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Ar—NH C NH—Ar S	Analysis			
						C%	H%	N%	S%
1.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	188-19	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ S	Found Calc.	59.20	3.78	10.68	12.21
						59.09	3.75	10.60	12.12
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	203	61	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	Found Calc.	60.12	4.70	10.78	12.34
						60.00	4.61	10.76	12.30
3.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	85	71	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	Found Calc.	49.14	3.21	17.64	10.11
						49.05	3.14	17.61	10.06
4.	2-Pyridyl	136	58	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	Found Calc.	57.46	4.38	24.48	13.58
						57.39	4.34	24.34	13.47
5.	<i>s</i> -Tribromophenyl	120	68	C ₁₃ H ₈ Br ₃ N ₂ S	Found Calc.	22.36	0.88	3.77	4.62
						22.22	0.85	3.98	4.55

3-*o*-Fluorophenyl-2-*o*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone :

sym-Di-*o*-fluorophenylthiourea (15 g.), monochloroacetic acid (5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (8 g.) and absolute ethanol (50 ml.) were refluxed together on a water bath for 4 hr. The excess of ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured in cold water, when a precipitate was obtained. The

precipitate was collected and washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted monochloroacetic acid and sodium acetate. After drying, it was recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals.

The analytical data and physical constants of other 4-thiazolidinones prepared by the above method are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. 3-ARYL-2-ARYL-IMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

S.No.	Ar	Colour	Molecular Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Analysis			Hydrochloride*			
						C%	H%	N%	M.P. %	Yield %	Method	
1.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl ^{a,b}	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ F ₂ OS	72	168	Found Calc.	59.14 59.02	3.29 3.28	9.42 9.21	182	88	A
2.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl ^{b,h}	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ F ₂ OS	66	124	Found Calc.	59.22 59.02	3.31 3.28	9.50 9.21	178	92	A
3.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl ^{c,h}	Brownish	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ Br ₂ OS	67	174	Found Calc.	42.00 42.25	2.86 2.66	6.79 6.57	196	81	A
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl ^h	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ Br ₂ OS	75	183*	Found Calc.	6.88 6.57	160	90	A
5.	<i>o</i> -Iodophenyl ^h	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ I ₂ OS	90	189	Found Calc.	34.68 34.61	1.40 1.92	5.48 5.38	174	85	A
6.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl ^{d,h}	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ I ₂ OS	85	215	Found Calc.	34.98 34.61	1.98 1.92	5.60 5.38	157	94	A
7.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl ⁱ	Shining white	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	58	179	Found Calc.	60.31 60.00	3.44 3.33	9.46 9.33	216	85	B
8.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl ^{e,i}	Yellowish brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	61	220	Found Calc.	60.42 60.00	3.40 3.33	9.51 9.33	215	82	B
9.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl ^{f,i}	Shining white	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	69	300	Found Calc.	60.46 60.00	3.29 3.33	9.42 9.33	274	90	B
10.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl ^g	Orange yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	65	78	Found Calc.	50.39 50.27	2.99 2.79	15.84 15.64	
11.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl ^g	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	68	108	Found Calc.	50.32 50.27	2.69 2.79	15.55 15.64	
12.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl ^g	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	68	176	Found Calc.	50.39 50.27	2.81 2.79	15.72 15.64	
13.	2-Pyridyl ^{g,h}	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	64	112	Found Calc.	62.34 62.22	3.62 3.70	20.83 20.74	
14.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl ^h	White	C ₁₅ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	76	64	Found Calc.	44.36 44.33	1.98 1.97	6.88 6.89	
15.	<i>s</i> -Tribromophenyl ^h	White	C ₁₅ H ₆ Br ₃ N ₂ OS	79	124	Found Calc.	24.35 24.25	0.86 0.83	3.86 3.77	

*Satisfactory analytical data for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and HCl were found for all the hydrochlorides.

This compound has been previously reported by Dains, Roy, Irvin and Harrel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921 **43, 613) and its m.p. is described as 183°.

a. i.r. absorption, CO, 1640 cm⁻¹; CN, 1500 cm⁻¹; CF, 1100 cm⁻¹.

b. u.v. absorption max. 238, 272 nm; i.r. absorption, CO, 1630 cm⁻¹; CN, 1499 cm⁻¹; CF, 1094 cm⁻¹;

c. i.r. absorption, CO, 1630 cm⁻¹; CN, 1470 cm⁻¹;

d. u.v. abs. max. 239, 283 nm.

e. i.r. absorption, OH, 1230, 3230 cm⁻¹; CO, 1630 cm⁻¹; CN, 1450 cm⁻¹.

f. u.v. abs. max. 257, 292 (sh) nm; i.r. absorption, OH, 1227, 3280 cm⁻¹; CO, 1650 cm⁻¹; CN, 1460 cm⁻¹.

g. u.v. abs. max. 262, 303 nm.

h. Recrystallised from ethanol.

i. Purified by dissolution in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitation with dilute hydrochloric acid.

j. Recrystallised from ethanol-water mixture.

Hydrochlorides of 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones were prepared by any one of the following two methods :

Method A : The 4-thiazolidinone was dissolved in minimum quantity of dry benzene and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through this solution for 30 min. when a gummy mass appeared. On keeping for sometime it changed to a crystalline form.

Method B : The 4-thiazolidinone was dissolved in excess of conc. hydrochloric acid and the solution was evaporated to give the hydrochloride.

The physical constants of all the 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinone hydrochlorides prepared, are given in Table 2.

Nematicidal activity :

(a) Tests were carried on *Meloidogyne Incognita* on tomato plants. Substances were mixed (30 mg./Kg.; 100 Kg/ha) with soil. Judgment of root system was made after four weeks.

(b) Judgment of phytotoxicity : 0 = No damage; 6 = Plant is dead.

TABLE 3—COMPOUND USED IS 3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONE

S.No.	Aryl group	Melo	Phyto	Remark	
1.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	2.0	0	100 Kg/ha	
		5.0			25 Kg/ha
		5.0			25 Kg/ha
2.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl	4.7	0		
3.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	Cannot be determined		6	
4.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Cannot be determined		6	
5.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	3.3	0		
6.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl*	4.5			

* This compound was used as its hydrochloride.

Insecticidal and acaricidal activity : 3-*p*-Bromophenyl-2-*p*-bromophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone and 3-*p*-iodophenyl-2-*p*-iodophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone were tested for insecticidal and acaricidal activities but none of them showed any activity.

Fungicidal activity : For fungicidal assay the method of Horsfall¹⁹ was used. The species *Alter-*

naria Solani was used as test fungus. The percentage inhibition was calculated by the following expression :

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{(Ac - At)}{Ac} \times 100$$

where Ac = Area of the colony in control plate.

At = Area of the colony in test plate.

Among all the compounds screened, compound Nos. 7, 13, 14, 15 in Table 2 and the hydrochloride of compound No. 7 (also in Table 2) showed considerable activity. Out of all these, 3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-imino-4-thiazolidinone was most active.

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